

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Development And Validation of RP-HPLC Method for The Simultaneous Determination of Olanzapine and Fluoxetine Hydrochloride in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms

N. Pravalika*, Dr. Mohammed Ibrahim, Rehmath Unnisa

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis and Quality Assurance, Prathap Narender Reddy College of Pharmacy, Peddashapur, Shamshabad

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 20 Mar 2026

Keywords:

Olanzapine, fluoxetine hydrochloride, validation.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19131096

ABSTRACT

A simple, sensitive and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of olanzapine and fluoxetine hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The mobile phase consisted of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer adjusted to pH 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid:Acetonitrile in the ratio of 40:60v/v delivered at a flow rate of 1ml/min and wavelength of UV detection at 235nm. The retention times of fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine were found to be 1.967 min and 5.740 min respectively. The linearity was observed and they were in the range of 10-50µg/ml and 5-25µg/ml for fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine respectively. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Olanzapine¹ is chemically, 2-methyl-4-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-10H-thieno[2,3-b] [1,5] benzodiazepine (Fig. 1a). It is an antipsychotic agent used in the treatment of schizophrenia. Fluoxetine hydrochloride² is chemically, methyl(3-phenyl-3-[4-(trifluoromethyl)phenoxy] propyl) amine hydrochloride (Fig. 1b). It is a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor used as an antidepressant agent with non-sedating

properties. Literature survey indicated very few methods like HPLC³, Spectroscopy⁴, HPTLC⁵ and Electron spray ionization tandem mass spectrometry⁶, for the simultaneous estimation of these drugs. Hence the combination of these drugs was selected for the simultaneous estimation by RP-HPLC method. The method presently developed has the advantage of being more sensitive to determine both the drugs concurrently

*Corresponding Author: N. Pravalika

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis and Quality Assurance, Prathap Narender Reddy College of Pharmacy, Peddashapur, Shamshabad

Email ✉: pravalika.scorpio@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

by simple and rapid RP-HPLC method for routine analysis.

FIGURE (1a). Structure of olanzapine

FIGURE (1b). Structure of fluoxetine hydrochloride

1. METHODOLOGY

2.1. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instrumentation : UV-3000⁺ LABINDIA Double beam with UV win 5 software UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1cm matched quartz cells was used to determine detection wavelength. WATERSHPLC Alliance 2695, UV-Visible Dual absorbance Detector 2487, with an automated sample injector. The output signal was monitored and integrated using Empower 2 software.

Chemicals and drugs: Acetonitrile, methanol and water are of HPLC grade and ortho phosphoric acid (OPA), pure potassium dihydrogen phosphate is of AR grade were obtained from Merck, Mumbai India. Fluoxetine Hydrochloride and Olanzapine reference standards were obtained as gift samples from Aurobindo Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad, India. Capsule dosage form

containing 25mg of fluoxetine hydrochloride and 12mg of olanzapine (SYMBYAX) was procured from the local market.

Chromatographic method: A Symmetry XTerra C18 (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μm) column was used for separations. The mobile phase considered was potassium dihydrogen phosphate:acetonitrile in the ratio of 40:60v/v buffer pH adjusted to 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid. It was pumped at the flow rate of 1ml/min. The mobile phase was passed through 0.45μm membrane filters and degassed before use. The eluent was monitored at 235nm and the injection volume was 20μl.

2.2. Preparation of solutions:

Preparation of Buffer Solution: 1.36 gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate was dissolved in 1000mL MilliQ water and pH of this solution was adjusted to 3.0 with ortho phosphoric acid. The solution was mixed well and then filtered through 0.45μ filter paper.

Preparation of Mobile phase: Mobile phase was prepared by mixing pH 3.0 buffer solution and acetonitrile in the ratio 40:60 v/v. Prior to use the mobile phase was filtered through 0.45μ membrane filter after sonication for 8 mins.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution of Olanzapine: Accurately weighed 100 mg of Olanzapine standard drug was transferred to 100 ml of volumetric flask. Then it was dissolved by adding a little amount of diluent. Mix it well, sonicate the solution and volume was made up to 100 ml. This is 1000μg/ml. From this solution 10 ml was transferred to another 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 100 ml with diluent(100μg/ml).

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution of Fluoxetine Hydrochloride: Accurately weighed 100 mg of Fluoxetine hydrochloride standard drug

was transferred to 100 ml of volumetric flask. Then it was dissolved by adding a little amount of diluent. Mix it well, sonicate the solution and volume was made up to 100 ml. This is 1000 μ g/ml. From this solution 10 ml was transferred to another 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 100 ml with diluent(100 μ g/ml).

Preparation of Working Standard Solution:

From the above stock solution 1.5ml of OLX solution and 3ml of FLX solution was transferred to 10 ml of volumetric flask and was made up to with mobile phase. The working standard solution produced contains 15 μ g/ml of OLZ and 30 μ g/ml of FLX.

Preparation of Sample Solution: Contents of twenty capsules were weighed accurately and average weight was recorded. 64mg of powder equivalent to 12.5mg of OLX and 25mg of FLX

was weighed accurately and transferred to 25ml volumetric flask and dissolved with mobile phase and sonicated for 10mins and filtered through 0.35 μ filter paper and volume made up to with mobile phase. The produced sample stock solution is (500 μ g/ml of OLX and 1000 μ g/ml of FLX). From this stock solution 0.3ml of solution was transferred to 10ml volumetric flask and made up to volume with mobile phase. The concentration of working solution consists of 15 μ g/ml of OLX and 30 μ g/ml of FLX.

2.3. Determination of Absorption maxima by uv/visible spectrophotometer:

Both the solutions of olanzapine and fluoxetine hydrochloride were scanned over the range of 190-400nm. Both the drugs showed good response at 235 nm, hence this wavelength was selected for further study. The overlaid uv spectra is shown in the figure 2.

Figure (2). Overlaid UV Spectra of olanzapine and fluoxetine hydrochloride

Detection: 235 nm

Injection volume: 20 μ l

2.4. Optimized Chromatographic conditions:

Stationary phase: Symmetry C₁₈ column (XTerra with 150 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile phase: potassium dihydrogen phosphate (pH 3.0): Acetonitrile (40:60) v/v

Flow rate: 1ml/min

Run time (min): 8 min

2.5. Procedure: Mixed standard solutions containing fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine in the range of 10 μ g/ml to 50 μ g/ml and 5 μ g/ml to 25 μ g/ml were prepared and each solution was injected in to the optimized chromatographic system. The chromatograms

were recorded and the peak areas were determined for each concentration of the drug solution. Calibration curve of fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine was obtained by plotting the peak areas versus the respective concentrations. The linear

correlation coefficient for fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine was found to be 0.999 and 0.999 respectively. A typical chromatogram of fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine was shown in Fig 3.

Figure (3). A typical chromatogram of fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine

3. VALIDATION STUDIES^{7,8}:

3.1. System suitability studies: The system suitability studies were done for parameters

like theoretical plates, tailing factor, repeatability, resolution and the results were given in the table 1.

Table (1). System suitability parameters

S.NO	PARAMETER	DRUG	OBSERVED VALUE
1.	Theoretical plates	Olanzapine	2350
		Fluoxetine Hcl	5160
2.	Tailing factor	Olanzapine	1.7
		Fluoxetine Hcl	1.3
3.	Retention time (min)	Olanzapine	5.734
		Fluoxetine Hcl	1.974
4.	Resolution	-----	5.6

3.2. Linearity studies: A series of standard solutions of different concentrations containing 10-50µg/ml of fluoxetine hydrochloride and 5-25µg/ml of olanzapine were prepared and 20µl of each standard was injected. The calibration curves were plotted by taking concentration on x-axis and peak areas on y-axis. The linearity data and calibration curve of the two drugs were given

the table 2 and 3 respectively and calibration curves in fig 4 and 5.

Table (2). Linearity data for Fluoxetine Hcl

SNO	Concentration(µg/ml)	Area
1	10	754573
2	20	1523860
3	30	2258968
4	40	2949416
5	50	3622377
	Correlation coefficient	0.999

Figure (4). Calibration curve of Fluoxetine HCl

Table (3). Linearity data for olanzapine

S.No	Concentration(µg/ml)	Area
1	5	567120
2	10	1090378

3	15	1570684
4	20	2047728
5	25	2484788
	Correlation coefficient	0.999

Figure (5). Calibration curve of Olanzapine

3.3. Precision studies: The system precision and method precision studies were done by using standard and sample solutions respectively. For precision the same

injection was repeatedly given and % RSD was calculated. The results were given in the table 4.

Table (4). Precision data for fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine

Injection	(Fluoxetine) Area	(Olanzapine) Area
Injection-1	2154484	1490945
Injection-2	2161125	1496948
Injection-3	2166753	1502679
Injection-4	2176050	1512282
Injection-5	2179032	1519006
Average	2167489	1504372

Standard Deviation	10206.66	11346.4
%RSD	0.47	0.75

3.4. Accuracy studies: The accuracy studies 50%, 100%, 150% and the recovery data was done by spiking the standard solutions to given in the table 5.

Table (5). Results of Recovery Studies:

Sample	accuracy	standard addition	formulation	% of recovery	statistical analysis
Fluoxetine Hcl	50%	15µg/ml	30 µg/ml	99.8%	SD=0.038 %RSD=1.26
	100%	30 µg/ml	30 µg/ml	101.3%	
	150%	45 µg/ml	30 µg/ml	101.5%	
Olanzapine	50%	7.5 µg/ml	15 µg/ml	100.6%	SD=0.047 %RSD=1.56
	100%	15 µg/ml	15 µg/ml	101.3%	
	150%	22.5 µg/ml	15	101.3%	

3.5. LOD and LOQ: The LOD and LOQ were separately determined based on the standard deviation of the response and the slope; the results are presented in table 6.

Table (6). Results of LOD and LOQ:

Parameter	FluoxetineHcl (µg/ml)	Olanzapine (µg/ml)
LOD	0.35	0.52
LOQ	1.064	1.586

3.6. Robustness studies: Robustness studies were done by changing the flow rate and the composition of mobile phase.

Table (7). Results of Robustness Studies:

Condition	variation	Average area (n=3)		%RSD	
		FLX	OLZ	FLX	OLZ
MOBILE PHASE phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (42:58) phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (40:60) phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (38:62) (40:60)v/v	phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (42:58)	2325609	1575908	0.49	0.33
	phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (40:60)	2235732	1535732	1.24	1.80
	phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): acetoneitrile (38:62)	2124504	1452138	0.28	0.70
FLOW RATE: 1ml/min	Less flow 0.9 ml/min	2332056	1631988	0.25	0.44
	Actual Flow 1.0 ml/min	2233850	1535732	0.18	1.80
	More Flow 1.1 ml/min	2136596	1448129	0.13	0.67

Assay: The proposed validated method was applied to determine fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine in commercial formulation and the results of assay were given in the table 8.

Table (8). Results of Analysis of Commercial formulation and recovery of proposed method

Formulation	Labeled claim (mg)	% of Assay
SYMBYAX	OLZ-12 µg/ml	100.90
	FLX- 25µg/ml	101.05

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To develop a new RP-HPLC method, several mobile phase compositions were tried. A satisfactory separation with good peak symmetry was obtained with C₁₈ (4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm, Make: XTerra) column using mobile phase containing potassium dihydrogen phosphate (pH 3.0): acetonitrile 40:60v/v at a flow rate of 1ml/min. Quantification was achieved with UV detection at 235 nm based on peak area. The retention time for fluoxetine hydrochloride and olanzapine were found to be 1.974 min and 5.740 min, respectively. The optimized method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The System suitability parameters observed by using this optimized conditions were reported. A linearity range of 10-50µg/ml with correlation coefficient 0.999 was established for fluoxetine hydrochloride and 5-25 µg/ml with correlation coefficient 0.999 was established for olanzapine. The precision of the proposed method was carried in terms of the repeatability and the %RSD values of fluoxetine hydrochloride was found to be 0.47% and of olanzapine was found to be 0.75% and reveal that the proposed method is precise. The LOD and LOQ values for fluoxetine hydrochloride were 0.35µg/ml, 1.0648µg/ml respectively and for olanzapine were found to be 0.52µg/ml, 1.586µg/ml. The study of robustness in the present method shows no significant changes either in the peak area or Rt. The results of analysis of commercial formulation indicated that there is

no interference due to common formulation excipients with the developed method. Therefore, the proposed method can be used for routine analysis of these two drugs in their combined pharmaceutical dosage form.

CONCLUSION

The proposed method was found to be simple, precise, accurate and rapid for determination of Fluoxetine hydrochloride and Olanzapine from pure and its dosage forms. The mobile phase is simple to prepare and economical. The sample recoveries in the formulation were in good agreement with their respective label claims and they suggested non-interference of formulation excipients in the estimation. Hence, this method can be easily and conveniently adopted for routine analysis of Fluoxetine hydrochloride and Olanzapine in pure form and its dosage form and also can be used for dissolution or similar studies.

REFERENCES

1. Indian Pharmacopoeia (2007) volume 3, 857.
2. United States Pharmacopeia 29 NF-24 volume 30(3), 848.
3. Rani, P.; Sekaran, B., Inter J of Pharmtech Research, (1), 654-57, (2009).
4. Rubesh, S.; Kiran, CH.; Duganath.N., (3), 52-55, (2011).
5. Patel, S.; Patel, NJ., Indian J of Pharm Sci, (73), 477, (2007).
6. Nirogi, RVS.; Kandikere, VN.; Mauryaa, S., J of Pharm and Biomed Anal, (41), 935-42, (2006).
7. ICH, Q2 (R1), Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology, International Conference on Harmonization, Geneva. 2005.
8. US FDA, Technical Review Guide: Validation of Chromatographic Methods, 1993.

HOW TO CITE: N. Pravalika, Dr. Mohammed Ibrahim, Rehmath Unnisa, Development And Validation of RP-HPLC Method for The Simultaneous Determination of Olanzapine and Fluoxetine Hydrochloride in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 3, 2239-2246. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19131096>

